

ZIGMA MEDICARE INDIA (OPC) PRIVATE LIMITED

No.26 A, Balaji Nagar, East Zone, Coimbatore – 641048

In Association with .,

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CONFERENCE PROCEEDINGS

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A Streamlit Tool For Airbnb Data Analysis And Visualization Insights.

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ABSTRACT :

This project presents a comprehensive analysis and visualization of Airbnb data using Streamlit, a powerful framework for building interactive web applications. By leveraging large-scale datasets, the analysis explores various aspects of Airbnb listings, such as location trends, pricing patterns, booking frequency, and guest reviews. Through dynamic visualizations and intuitive interactive features, the application enables users to gain insights into factors influencing pricing, demand, and user experience across different regions. The project aims to provide an accessible tool for stakeholders in the hospitality and tourism sectors to make data-driven decisions and enhance understanding of the Airbnb market landscape.

Keywords: Airbnb Analytics, Streamlit Dashboard, Short-term Rental Trends, Data Visualization, Pricing Analysis, Customer Insights, Geographic Distribution, Machine Learning in Hospitality, Travel and Tourism Data, Interactive Data Exploration, Seasonal Demand Analysis, Real Estate Market Insights

1. INTRODUCTION :

The rapid growth of Airbnb has revolutionized the global hospitality industry, offering

travelers a wide array of unique accommodations while providing hosts with an opportunity to monetize their properties. However, understanding the factors that drive Airbnb's success, including pricing strategies, demand fluctuations, and customer preferences, requires in-depth data analysis. This project focuses on the analysis and visualization of Airbnb data through Streamlit, an open-source framework that facilitates the creation of interactive, web-based applications.

2. PROBLEM IDENTIFICATION :

As the Airbnb market continues to expand globally, both hosts and guests face increasing challenges in navigating and understanding the complexities of the platform. For hosts, determining optimal pricing strategies, understanding demand patterns, and identifying profitable locations can be difficult without access to comprehensive data analysis. Guests, on the other hand, may struggle to find the best value for their stays, given the vast number of available listings and the variability in pricing across different regions. Additionally, the ability to assess the quality of listings through reviews and ratings is often fragmented, making it harder to make informed decisions.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY :

The first step in the research methodology was to gather relevant Airbnb data. Publicly available datasets, such as those from Inside Airbnb and Kaggle, were utilized. These datasets contain a range of variables, including information on listings (e.g., price, location, type of property), host details, guest reviews, and booking patterns. The data spans multiple cities and regions, providing a diverse sample to analyze. The core of the project focused on data analysis and visualization. Using Python libraries such as Pandas, Matplotlib, and Seaborn, several analytical techniques were employed to extract actionable insights from the data:

3.1 Price prediction models: Implementing regression models to predict listing prices based on features like location, property type, and amenities.

3.2 Trend analysis: Analyzing seasonal trends and demand fluctuations in various regions.

3.3 Geospatial analysis: Mapping listing distribution across different neighborhoods and regions using geographical data.

3.4 User testing: Gathering feedback from potential users (e.g., Airbnb hosts, travelers, and industry experts) to ensure the application was user-friendly and met their needs.

3.5 Model accuracy: Evaluating the accuracy of predictive models by comparing predicted prices against actual listing prices.

Fig (1) Map View.

	April 2023 List Price
Highest Price	\$10000.00
Average Price	\$227.55
Lowest Price	\$20.00

Fig (2) : Data List.

4. METHOD OF COMPARISON :

One of the primary aspects analyzed was the pricing trends for Airbnb listings across different cities and regions. To compare price variability, the following approaches were used:

4.1 City-wise price comparison: The average price per night for listings in various cities or neighborhoods was calculated and compared to identify high-demand, high-price areas versus more affordable regions.

4.2 Price distribution: Box plots and histograms were used to compare the distribution of prices in different locations, highlighting variations in pricing patterns and the presence of outliers.

4.3 Correlation analysis: The relationship between price and other factors (e.g., location, property type, amenities) was analyzed to determine the key drivers of price in different regions.

5. CONCLUSION :

This project provided a comprehensive analysis and visualization of Airbnb data, utilizing Streamlit to create an interactive platform for users to explore key trends and insights. Through detailed data cleaning, exploratory analysis, and geospatial mapping, the study uncovered significant patterns in pricing, demand, and host performance across various cities and regions. The findings reveal that factors such as location, property type, amenities, and seasonal trends play crucial roles in determining pricing and demand for Airbnb listings.

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